

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF INTERPHASES PROPERTIES: A CRUCIAL PART IN THE DEGRADATION OF A UD COMPOSITES

L. Belec¹, Y. Joliff¹, T.H. Nguyen², J.F. Chailan¹

¹Laboratoire Matériaux Polymère Interface Environnement Marin (MAPIEM EA 4323), University of Toulon, BP20132, 83957 La Garde Cedex, France
Email: belec@univ-tln.fr, web page: <http://www.mapiem.univ-tln.fr>

²Danang College of Technology, University of Danang, VietNam
web page: <http://www.udn.vn/english>

Keywords: Finite Element Analysis, Interphases, Natural Ageing

ABSTRACT

The impact of humid tropical weathering on simplified glass fibre–epoxy composites is characterized at different scales. The unidirectional composite is analyzed by AFM force measurements at matrix/fibre interface and three point bending tests in transverse mode to quantify the matrix/fibre interfacial strength. A specific area of around 500 nm width can be identified as the interphase. This area presents a gradient of elastic modulus attributes to lower crosslink density in the interphase compared to the surrounding matrix. A realistic microstructure is considered to model the composite. The local modulus values are input in the finite element model. The macroscopic three point bending test is then simulated under ABAQUS software. The comparison between numerical data and experimental values at initial state enables the quantification of local stress values associated to the ultimate stress at break. The same method is applied after several months of exposure in humid tropical conditions. The numerical simulation of the bending test during ageing is correlated to the evolutions of elastic modulus of the composite interphases

1 INTRODUCTION

The properties of composite materials at initial state and their evolutions under wet service conditions are highly influenced by the interphase created between the matrix and the reinforcement [1,2]. Specific techniques operating at sub-micron scale such as AFM and nanoindentation are used to characterize interphases in organic matrix composites [3–8]. In most cases, due to high indentation depth, boundary effects often lead to an increase of elastic modulus close to fibre surface. Other techniques show the opposite behavior attributed to a matrix network undercrosslinked around fibres or plasticizing effects resulting from fibre silane treatment [9–11]. The interphase molecular mobility is then higher than the bulk matrix one, which influences water diffusion and solubility of the composite material [12]. The effects of hygrothermal ageing on epoxy matrix are also well known in terms of water sorption, plasticizing effect, swelling phenomena or formation of microcracks through absorption/desorption cycles [13].

Natural exposure in sunny environments combined the effects of hygrothermal ageing and UV ageing, widely described in the last decades in the case of amine-epoxy systems [14–17]. Competitive effects between chain scission and crosslinking processes under photo-oxidation have recently been identified by nanoindentation and microhardness tests on epoxy resins surfaces [18]. In humid tropical conditions, precipitations on epoxy laminates can leach out free constituents resulting from chain scission for example [19].

Most studies concern homogeneous epoxy resins, without considering the interphase specific properties. The characterization of interphases before and after ageing by AFM force measurements has been made and could be correlated to macroscopic evolutions [20].

Some finite element models with interphase are reported in the literature. Mortazavi et al. [21] have shown by a numerical approach the impact of the interphase on elastic properties applied of nanocomposite. Jiang et al. [22] proposed a micro-mechanics model based on Mori-Tanaka method to describe the mechanical properties of composites reinforced by regularly distributed particles with an inhomogeneous interphase. Maligno et al. [23] investigated local damage in unidirectional (UD) composite materials with epoxy resin under transverse tensile loading by a 3D micromechanical study. The aim of the present study is to implement the mechanical data obtained at nano and macroscale into a finite element model to identify the initiation of damage within the composite. The longer term objective is to predict the initiation of damage in correlation with degradation kinetics.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The composite matrix is a stoichiometric blend of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) prepolymer $n=0.13$ and a Diethylene Triamine (DETA) hardener from Aldrich. The matrix is reinforced by E glass fibres coated by a γ -aminopropylsilane simplified (APS) sizing. 2 mm thick unidirectional plates with 20-25 wt % fibres were moulded with an optimized curing cycle (2 hrs at 60 °C followed by 2 hrs at 120 °C and 2 hrs at 140°C).

3.1 Ageing conditions

Specimens were exposed up to 19 months in Danang (16°10'N), Vietnam, in humid tropical conditions. The annual radiation was 6424 MJ/m² with a mean relative humidity (RH) of 82.3% (+/- 4 %). The mean temperatures were 29.8 °C (+/- 3.6 °C) for the maximum and 22.6 °C (+/- 2.3 °C) for the minimum.

3.2 Techniques

To characterize the matrix/fibre interfacial strength, the three-point bending test was used in transverse mode with a MTS DY35 universal tensile equipment according to the standard NF EN 2746. Each value is an average of five measurements and the standard deviations are around 5 % and 15 % for the modulus and data at break respectively.

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) was performed on a Nanoscope V controller equipped with a Multimode V microscope and a 8610 JVLR type scanner. Tapping mode cantilever probes (RTESP model from BRUKER) were used for the force measurements with a constant spring around 40 N/m adapted to epoxy stiffness. The system sensitivity and cantilever spring constant k_c were measured for each probe [24]. The samples were cut perpendicularly to fibre axis and polished up to 1 μ m with diamond grinding paste. AFM force curves were performed in the elastic range with maximum forces lower than 1 μ N to limit sample indentation and improve lateral resolution. The mean values and standard deviation are calculated on 10 measurements. The elastic modulus was estimated from force curves in the linear elastic range using Hertz model.

3.3 Finite Element Analysis

The numerical model developed is based on optical microscopy observations of a real sample (Figure 1a). Indeed, in previous studies, the impact of distribution has been clearly shown [25-26]. This method takes account of contacts between fibres, which represent a barrier effect to water diffusion. Moreover, the proximity between two fibres leads to stress concentration [12]. The numerical sample of the three point bending test is realized from the assembly of many unit cells (Figure 1b) up to obtain the size of the experimental sample. Around each fibre, an interphase area is added in agreement with the experimental measurements. The properties of each part (matrix, interphase and fibre), used in the numerical model, have been taken from experimental data.

The mesh has been done from triangular elements with quadratic interpolation to fit the circular shape shape of the fibre and the matrix cavities.

Due to symmetry only one half of the three-point bending test has been simulated. The bending tools have been described by rigid elements (no strain allowed). The span cylinder is fixed in all

directions while the upper cylinder can be moved only in vertical direction. The contact between the tools surfaces and the sample surfaces has been defined by a surface to surface contact based on master/slave surfaces. The tangential properties of these contacts have been supposed without friction due to the small displacements involved.

Figure 1. Fibres distribution in the composite (a) from Scanning Electron Microscopy observation and (b) as modelled for numerical simulation (unit cell)

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Evolutions at macroscopic scale

At initial state, the comparison between the strain and stress at break values for the resin and the composite (Table 1) shows that the introduction of fibres leads to a fragile behavior of the material in transverse direction.

	RESIN				COMPOSITE		
	Ageing time	E(MPa)	σ_R (MPa)	ϵ_R (%)	E(MPa)	σ_R (MPa)	ϵ_R (%)
NA (months)	0	1423	59	4.5	2059	41	1.78
	3	1807	96	8.3	2370	39	1.44
	8	1736	30	1.5	1994	36	1.49
	19	-	-	-	2033	33	1.35

Table 1: Flexural values for the composite and resin measured by transverse bending test during ageing

During ageing, the mean values at break of the resin increase up to 12 weeks of natural ageing (Table 1) while the composite strength decreases during the same period. The mechanical response of fibre/matrix interface is then more impacted by ageing effects than the matrix. Conversely, a similar evolution is observed for the composite and resin elastic modulus values during ageing. The elastic response is mainly attributed to the matrix deformation while data at break mainly reflect matrix/fibre interfacial response. Beyond 12 weeks the modulus and data at break of the composite and the resin decrease due to a degradation of the epoxy network.

4.2 Interphases evolution during ageing

AFM force measurements are performed at increasing distance from fibre surface (Figure 2). At initial state, the elastic moduli are around 50 % lower than the mean value measured beyond 1 μm from fibre surface. This modified network defines an interphase of around 500 nm width.

After 19 months of natural weathering, a huge impact is shown at fibre vicinity and inside the matrix. The interphase width is increased above 1 μm with a lower elastic modulus, especially for fibres located below 20 μm from composite surface. The impact is less pronounced deeper inside the

composite. The matrix modulus is also divided by 10 near the surface and by 2 deeper into the composite.

Figure 2. Evolution of Young's modulus measured by AFM force curves at increasing distance from fibres surface at initial state and after 19 months of natural ageing (at 20 µm and 200 µm from composite surface).

4.3 Numerical simulation of the 3 point bending test

To reduce the calculating time, 3 models defined by the 3 scales factors f (1/4, 1/6, 1/8) have been developed. For each model, the maximum stresses generated by the model decrease highly with the increase of the scale factor f according to equation 1:

$$\sigma(f) = 21. f^{-1.31} \quad (1)$$

For this study, the 1/8 scale was used for numerical simulation of the 3 point bending test (Figure 3). The stress values for scale 1 are then extrapolated from equation 1.

Figure 3. Numerical simulation of the 3 point bending test at scale 1/8 (σ_{Mises}) at t_0

To simulate the behavior of aged samples, we consider that fibres are not be affected by ageing conditions. Initial mechanical properties of the matrix, interphase are used for the numerical model at initial state. In agreement with experimental results, lower mechanical properties of the matrix and interphase were used for aged samples. Results from numerical and experimental analysis are superimposed in Figure 4. Numerical results are always lower than experimental values but the gap

between the two methods is low. This gap can be explained by the difference between fibre volume fraction of the experimental sample and the numerical model. Moreover, the distribution of fibres is more inhomogeneous in experimental samples compared to numerical samples which are built from a stack of unit cells (Figure 1).

During the ageing of the composite sample, the stress at break is decreased by 35 % compared to the value at initial state.

Figure 4. Comparison between experimental and numerical results of the three bending test

5 CONCLUSIONS

The characterization of mechanical properties of a simplified UD composite from nano- to macro-scale shows the existence of an interphase area around fibres which fragilises the material during 3 point bending test in tranverse mode. The composite strength is directly dependant of interphase properties and of their evolutions. During tropical ageing, the drop of elastic moduli is even more pronounced in these areas. The interphase width is also increased, especially at composite surface. Cracks are probably initiated in the interphases which are in tension during the bending test. The decrease of composite strength can then be correlated to the evolution of interphase properties during ageing. These assumptions can be confirmed by the numerical analysis of the bending test. The composite sample is modeled with a realistic microstructure taking account of fibre distribution and interphase characteristics. In a first step, different scales of analysis were considered. The simulation shows the most loaded areas which enables in a first approximation, the determination of local critical stress values.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hodzic, J.K. Kim, A.E. Lowe, Z.H. Stachurski, The effects of water aging on the interphase region and interlaminar fracture toughness in polymer–glass composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **64**, 2004, pp. 2185–2195.
- [2] C. Griswold, W.M. Cross, L. Kjerengtroen, J.J. Kellar, Interphase variation in silane-treated glass-fiber-reinforced epoxy composites, *J. Adhes. Sci. Technol.* **19**, 2005, pp. 279–290.
- [3] R. Plonka, E. Mader, S.L. Gao, C. Bellmann, V. Dutschk, S. Zhandarov, Adhesion of epoxy / glass fibre composites influenced by aging effects on sizings, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* **35**, 2004, pp. 1207–1216.

- [4] M. Kharrat, A. Chateauminois, L. Carpentier, P. Kapsa, On the interfacial behaviour of a glass / epoxy composite during a micro-indentation test : assessment of interfacial shear strength using reduced indentation curves, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* **28**, 1996, pp. 39–46.
- [5] D.A. Jesson, J.F. Watts, The interface and interphase in polymer matrix composites: Effect on mechanical properties and methods for identification., *Polym. Rev.* **52**, 2012, pp. 321–354.
- [6] V. Cech, E. Palesch, J. Lukes, The glass fiber–polymer matrix interface/interphase characterized by nanoscale imaging techniques, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **83**, 2013, pp. 22–26.
- [7] T.J. Young, L.E. Crocker, W.R. Broughton, S.L. Ogin, P. a. Smith, Observations on interphase characterisation in polymer composites by nano-scale indentation using AFM and FEA, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* **50**, 2013, pp. 39–43.
- [8] C.D. Wood, M.J. Palmeri, K.W. Putz, G. Ho, R. Barto, L. Catherine Brinson, Nanoscale structure and local mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites containing MWCNT-grafted hybrid glass fibers, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **72**, 2012, pp. 1705–1710.
- [9] W.M. Cross, F. Johnson, J. Mathison, C. Griswold, J.J. Kellar, L. Kjerengtroen, The effect of interphase curing on interphase properties and formation, *J. Adhes.* **78**, 2002, pp. 571–590.
- [10] S. Mallarino, J.F. Chailan, J.L. Vernet, Sizing effects on main relaxation process of cyanate ester glass fiber composites using Dynamic Mechanical and Microthermal Analyses, *J. Polym. Sci. Part B.* **44**, 2005, pp. 205–214.
- [11] G. Van Assche, B. Van Mele, Interphase formation in model composites studied by microthermal analysis, *Polymer (Guildf)*. **43**, 2002, pp. 4605–4610.
- [12] Y. Joliff, W. Rekik, L. Belec, J.F. Chailan, Study of the moisture/stress effects on glass fibre/epoxy composite and the impact of the interphase area, *Compos. Struct.* **108**, 2014, pp. 876–885.
- [13] F.X. Perrin, M.H. Nguyen, J.L. Vernet, Water transport in epoxy–aliphatic amine networks – Influence of curing cycles, *Eur. Polym. J.* **45**, 2009, pp. 1524–1534.
- [14] V. Bellenger, J. Verdu, Photooxidation of Amine Crosslinked Epoxies II. Influence of Structure, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **28**, 1983, pp. 2677–2688.
- [15] F. Delor-Jestin, D. Drouin, P.-Y. Cheval, J. Lacoste, Thermal and photochemical ageing of epoxy resin - Influence of curing agents, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* **91**, 2006, pp. 1247–1255.
- [16] B. Mailhot, S. Morlat-Therias, M. Ouahioune, J.-L. Gardette, Study of the Degradation of an Epoxy/Amine Resin, 1 Photo- and Thermo-Chemical Mechanisms, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **206**, 2005, pp. 575–584.
- [17] D.R. Bauer, Interpreting weathering acceleration factors for automotive coatings using exposure models, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* **69**, 2000, pp. 307–316.
- [18] J.-F. Larché, P.-O. Bussière, S. Thérias, J.-L. Gardette, Photooxidation of polymers: Relating material properties to chemical changes, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* **97**, 2012, pp. 25–34.
- [19] N.K. Sookay, C.J. von Klemperer, V.E. Verijenko, Environmental testing of advanced epoxy composites, *Compos. Struct.* **62**, 2003, pp. 429–433.
- [20] L. Belec, T.H. Nguyen, D.L. Nguyen, J.F. Chailan Comparative effects of humid tropical weathering and artificial ageing on a model composite properties from nano- to macro-scale. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **68**, 2015, pp. 235-241
- [21] B. Mortazavi, J. Bardon, S. Ahzi, Interphase effect on the elastic and thermal conductivity response of polymer nanocomposite materials: 3D finite element study, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **69**, 2013, pp. 100–106
- [22] Y. Jiang, K. Tohgo, Y. Shimamura, A micro-mechanics model for composites reinforced by regularly distributed particles with an inhomogeneous interphase, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **46**, 2009, pp. 507–515.
- [23] A.R. Maligno, N.A. Warrior, A.C. Long effects of interphase material properties in unidirectional fibre reinforced composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **70**, 2010, pp. 36–44

- [24] H.-J. Butt, B. Cappella, M. Kappl, Force measurements with the atomic force microscope: Technique, interpretation and applications, *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **59**, 2005, pp. 1–152.
- [25] Y. Joliff, L. Belec, M.B. Heman, J.F. Chailan, Experimental, analytical and numerical study of water diffusion in unidirectional composite materials – Interphase impact, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **64**, 2012, pp. 141–145.
- [26] Y. Joliff, L. Belec, J.F. Chailan, Modified water diffusion kinetics in an unidirectional glass / fibre composite due to the interphase area : Experimental , analytical and numerical approach, *Compos. Struct.* **97**, 2013, pp. 296–303.